

Argentina Experimental HEP Input

Contribution from Buenos Aires and La Plata groups to the Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure

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This document is sent on behalf of the academic faculty members and researchers of the High Energy Physics (HEP) Groups at Universidad de Buenos Aires (UBA-CONICET) and Universidad Nacional de La Plata (UNLP-CONICET). The main goal of these HEP groups is the search for new physics by a synergy of theoretical exploration and experimental innovation in the framework of the ATLAS experiment at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) in the current phase, and in the approved High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), as well as in experiments of future colliders in the field.

Scientific Context - International Experiments (LHC, HL-LHC and future accelerators)

The goal of Particle Physics is to understand the elementary composition and the basic laws of Nature. Among its recent experimental discoveries, the Higgs boson in 2012, appears to represent the summit in the successful experimental verification of the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics. However, although essentially all of the data from particle accelerators are so far in perfect agreement with the model's predictions, a number of important theoretical and observational considerations point to the necessity of physics beyond the SM (BSM).

The Higgs boson opens a whole new scalar sector of fundamental particles, distinct from the vector and spin-half fermion families known up to now. In addition to advancing our understanding of the electroweak symmetry breaking and mass generation mechanism for fundamental particles, its study could potentially act as a portal to otherwise inaccessible sectors. This requires tests of the compatibility of the 125 GeV state with the SM in as many decay modes as possible, searches for rare and exotic decay modes, for unexpected production modes and, in the longer term, detailed studies of the Higgs-self coupling.

The origin of electroweak symmetry breaking poses a number of theoretical questions like naturalness, fine tuning or hierarchy. Although the once favorite explanation, electroweak (EW) scale supersymmetry (SUSY), looks to be in trouble, these questions have not gone away. Many alternative BSM scenarios require new particles or effects close to the EW scale, and their search is the major goal of the LHC in the following two decades. But the central business of this field has always been to search for previously unobserved effects at the energy frontier. Collider exploration of particle physics significantly beyond the EW scale has no clear indication of the energies at which new physics will appear. It is an open question what is the mass reach and intensity at which we are going to be able to probe.

The LHC and HL-LHC are the only energy frontier facilities that actually exist and/or

are approved addressing many of the scientific areas above. The upgrade of the LHC to the HL-LHC will provide a unique opportunity for detailed studies of electroweak symmetry breaking, and for searching for physics beyond the SM. Major upgrades of the LHC experiments, in particular ATLAS where Argentinean HEP groups presenting this proposal are members since 2006, are required to cope with the HL-LHC conditions and to fully exploit its physics potential. Argentina is committed to the ATLAS upgrade for the HL-LHC with contributions to the trigger electronics, Data Acquisition, High-Level trigger software and hardware, and photon/electron/tau/jet reconstruction.

Given that we are a growing community, our experimental strategy is to continue building strength in areas that will be applicable in any future effort in the energy frontier. This implies efforts both in detector research and development (R&D), and in analysis that is expected to be relevant and of quality impact to future accelerators that the community might decide to build. For both scientific and strategic reasons, the planned FCC-hh makes the most sense from the current perspective. Our experimental HEP community is supportive of such future collider which is crucial for the advancement of particle physics and will continue to be so for the foreseeable future and we plan to participate in development of its future detector projects.

Objectives and Experimental efforts

Our groups are members since 2006 of the ATLAS experiment at the LHC of the CERN laboratory. The LHC collides counterrotating proton beams with up to 14 TeV center of mass energy, and counts two main detectors, ATLAS and CMS. These two state-of-the-art experiments have since their inception the objective of pushing the frontier of knowledge in high energy physics. Full Institutional Members have full rights and obligations in the Collaboration. In particular, they are represented in the Collaboration Board. This is an assembly of all ATLAS Institutions, where major decisions for the collaboration are discussed and voted on. Every Institution is equal, with one vote each. ATLAS Institutions are expected to contribute to the Operation and Maintenance (M&O), to Operation Tasks (OT), and physics programme of the ATLAS experiment, as well as to the detector upgrade programme for operation at the High-Luminosity LHC. The responsibilities of our groups in ATLAS have included so far participating in the online testing of data taking, the development of the programs for the online selection of events, the calibration of detectors, the measurement and improvement of their performance, as well as the pursuit of multiple lines of physics analysis, several of them as leaders of the respective analysis teams.

Our main interests have concentrated on event triggering, reconstruction and physics analyses based on photons and/or jets. These have included SM precision measurements, and searches for supersymmetry and other BSM models. The list of subjects addressed in PhD Theses by students in our groups serve as description of the physics objectives carried on up to now:

- Search for extra spatial dimensions: study of the two-photon final state
- Measurement of the inclusive isolated prompt photon production
- Determination of the electron and gamma trigger efficiency
- Production of the J/ψ particle in the electron-positron channel
- Search for Supersymmetry in events with a photon, jets and missing energy
- Study of the Higgs boson properties in the diphoton channel
- Search for Supersymmetry in events with a photon, electro/muon and missing energy

- Supersymmetry search in final states with missing energy and at least three b -jets
- Identification of b -jets produced by gluon splitting
- Search of supersymmetric particles in multi-jet events with missing energy
- Measurement of four-jet differential cross sections in
- Measurement of the inclusive jet cross-section
- Search for resonances decaying into a photon and a jet
- Measurement of the dijet mass differential cross-section

Below we discuss experimental efforts relevant to the Latinamerican Strategy, that Argentinean researchers in ATLAS are actively involved with or are expecting to be involved with in the future.

Detector and Electronics R&D:

The ATLAS experiment is entering a new era, an upgrade program to meet the 4-fold increase in luminosity that the HL-LHC will start delivering in 2026. The need to select potentially interesting events with pile-up of up to 200 inelastic collisions per bunch crossing will place stringent constraints on the Trigger and Data Acquisition (TDAQ) system. The so-called Phase-II upgrade of the TDAQ system will enable the broad physics programme planned for the HL-LHC, including a detailed exploration of the mechanism of electroweak symmetry breaking through the properties of the Higgs boson, searches for new physics through the study of rare Standard Model processes, searches for new heavy states, and measurements of the properties of any newly discovered particles.

The Argentinian institutions are involved in the design, construction and tests of the Global Trigger component of the first part of the trigger, the hardware based Level-0. The Global Trigger is a sub-system receiving and processing trigger primitives from Calorimeter and Muon systems. It also uses full granularity calorimeter information to refine calorimeter objects and performs topology-based multi-object selections. It provides refined Level-0 objects to Central Trigger Processor. Its purpose is to incorporate at Level-0 capabilities that in Phase-I were only available in the much slower software-based Event Filter at the High-Level Trigger. The emphasis in the Global Trigger is overwhelmingly on firmware rather than on hardware.

The typical time period from first prototypes to large system deployment for detector R&D requires a different funding mind-set and better coordination in Argentina and across LA, to avoid sub-critical levels of investment.

The very significant potential of technologies developed for particle physics to continue to bring benefit to the society, and to benefit from technologies developed for other applications, needs to be better understood in LA. We need a more coordinated approach across LA to supporting technology transfer developments, recognising the need and impact for sustained investment.

Machine Learning:

Machine Learning, in particular Deep Learning, is becoming a common tool in HEP. The Argentinean ATLAS groups are involved in applying these tools in current and near future analyses (for instance in jet tagging, fast simulation, calorimeter calibration, and more), and we foresee a much heavier involvement and usage of our community in Artificial Intelligence tools. This requires preparation, both in terms of peripheral computing and software power but also in terms of education and supporting human resources.

Comment on the need for non-academic professionals in HEP experiments :

Future HEP experiments will require increasing sophistication of electronics and software. For software and electronic engineers, even the flexibility of academia often cannot compensate for the higher salaries and attractive challenges of industry. Physicists who do become experts in these fields have trouble getting stable positions and therefore are forced to leave academia, taking with them crucial knowledge that new hires cannot provide. These two factors, already a problem, endanger the ability to build and maintain future experiments. Ways for academic institutions to provide stable employment and more competitive salaries for these crucial professionals must be found.

Methodology

The TDAQ Upgrade Project is defined in detail in the Technical Design Report (TDR) (<https://cds.cern.ch/record/2285584>). The Project consists of a number of sub-units and deliverables, which are organised in a detailed Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) used for all project management purposes.

The Global Trigger complements the L0 Calo trigger objects with additional high granularity energy data coming directly from upgraded calorimeter pre-processors. This allows the implementation of offline-like algorithms. Furthermore, the Global Trigger will replace and extend the functionality of the L1Topo system, applying topological selections to trigger objects. The implementation of the Global Trigger consists of three primary components: a Multiplexer Processor (MUX) layer, a Global Event Processor (GEP) layer, and a demultiplexing Global-to-CTP Interface, all of which have identical hardware composed of ATCA blades and FPGAs with many multi-gigabit transceivers. Both the calorimeter and muon detector sub-systems, FEXs and MUCTPI respectively, provide serial data for each bunch crossing to the MUX layer. These signals are then timemultiplexed and the signals for a given event are transported to a single GEP node that executes the algorithms. Finally, the results are sent to the CTP through the CTP Interface. The Production Firmware Deployment Modules (PFM) will be used to evaluate and validate firmware blocks before deployment, and to facilitate regular firmware upgrades during future operations.

Argentina Commitments:

1. Design, production and testing of Common Modules (a common hardware module with different functionality implemented in firmware, composed of ATCA blades and FPGAs with many multi-gigabit transceivers);
2. Development of algorithmic firmware and software;
3. Design, production, testing; installation and commissioning of Rear Transition Modules (RTM);
4. Design, production, testing, installation and commissioning of Fibre Management;
5. Procurement of general infrastructure.

Timeline/Construction&OperatingCosts/ComputingRequirements

The HL-LHC is expected to start operations in the middle of 2026, and to reach nominally a peak instantaneous luminosity of $L = 5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, corresponding to approximately

up to 200 inelastic proton-proton collisions per bunch crossing. This poses a challenge on the readout electronics of all subdetectors and also to the Trigger and Data acquisition system. The Phase-II upgraded trigger system needs to maintain legacy hardware, where appropriate, accommodate new detectors and exploit the full granularity provided by the detectors. The rate of accepted events by the hardware trigger must be of 1 MHz and a maximum fixed latency of 10 μ s. This imposes unprecedented technological challenges in the design and building of the hardware trigger that we will face in our electronics lab in collaboration with international partners.

The installation of the HEP laboratory at Instituto de Fisica La Plata (IFLP, UNLP-CONICET) as part of the LA infrastructure for HEP experiments, is being set up in the new IFLP building. The first stage consists mainly of an electronics laboratory for development and deploying of hardware for high speed, real time signal processing. The laboratory is being equipped and we expect to be fully operational by the end of 2020. Besides a group of physicists, we have hired a full time electronic engineer that will start working in charge of the lab after finishing his training at CERN in mid 2020, and a part time computer engineer. Some of the equipment that this lab will have when fully operational includes:

- FPGA evaluation Kits
- High performance computers for firmware synthesis
- Soldering station and tools for handling fine pitch PCBs SMD components
- High speed oscilloscopes and high speed function generators
- ATCA shelf
- High speed optic fibers management

The aim of the lab is to have enough resources and technology to help developing, testing and deploying high speed signal electronics with enough performance to be used for data acquisition on High Energy Physics experiments. In particular, this equipment will allow in a first step the development of electronics for the new hardware trigger for the ATLAS experiment at the HL-LHC and for future developments for HEP detectors as well as other applications in different fields (Astrophysics, Satellites, telecommunications, etc).

The following figure (Figure 1) shows the LHC timeline indicating the periods when the hardware, in particular that developed in Argentina, should be ready and installed.

Funding:

- Local Laboratory: Besides the funds for finishing setting up the electronic HEP laboratory at IFLP, it is important recognising the need for sustained investment. In a very competitive funding environment, national-level projects often get sufficient resources to achieve promising initial results but then cannot secure the necessary funding to take this forward. It is crucial to transmit to the national science and technology authorities the message of the benefit from these technologies and known-how to other applications.
- CORE costs: A MOU has been signed between CERN and Secretaría de Ciencia, Tecnología and Innovación Productiva, Argentina on July 2, 2019. This takes effect from the date of signature and remains valid until completion of Long Shutdown 3 (currently scheduled for 2026). The CORE Argentinean contribution to the construction of the ATLAS Trigger/DAQ Phase-II Upgrade amounts 759k CHF devoted to the Argentinean commitments described above.

Figure 1: LHC timeline

- Operating Costs in ATLAS: Institutions are expected to contribute to the M&O. There is a yearly share of M&O costs of around 10 kCHF per author (or qualifying author) holding a PhD or equivalent. In addition, a common fund contribution of about 1.5 kCHF per M&O author, per year is paid during the High-Luminosity LHC detector upgrade phase (2018-2025). There are no M&O payments for students.
- Operation Tasks: Institutions take on a share of the OT, such as shifts or data quality monitoring, and corresponding institutional commitments. For the OT requirements students are also included, however with a lower weight of 0.75. Most of these activities are carried on in-situ at the site of the experiment ATLAS, CERN. It is important to have the necessary funds to support Argentinean groups on its missions to CERN. Funds are needed (per diem and air ticket) to allow the presence of Argentinean ATLAS members to participate of the on-site activities of the experiments.
- Mobility: HEP experiments require complex and sophisticated instrumentation. For the researchers, students, engineers, technician working on these experiments, international mobility is an essential issue.
- Computing: At the most conservative estimates, ATLAS produces and transfers over 400 PB of data per year requiring millions of CPU to process and analyse and to generate large Monte Carlo datasets. The collaboration is worldwide, and only Grid allows all collaborators to have access to the full datasets. The Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) is composed of four levels, or Tiers. Each Tier is made up of several computer centres and provides a specific set of services. Between them the Tiers process, store and analyse all the data from ATLAS. Tier 0 is the CERN Data Centre. Tier 1 consists of computer centres large enough to store LHC data, distributing data to Tier 2s, and storing a share of the simulated data that the Tier 2s produce. Individual scientists can access the Grid through local (or Tier 3) computing resources, which can consist of local clusters in a university department. Funds are needed for the purchase of CPU ($\sim 5\text{-}7\text{kHS06}$ (CPU) and ~ 1 PB (Storage) to be able to have at least a Tier-3 facility in our country.